

FAIR Scientific Knowledge Exchange (FSKX)-Cloud-Platform: A Microservice- Based Solution for Scientific Model Execution

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Executive Summary

The FAIR Scientific Knowledge Exchange (FSKX) format has established itself as a valuable standard for the exchange of data and models across scientific domains. Originally developed as the Food Safety Knowledge Exchange format, it has evolved beyond the food safety domain to facilitate adoption across multiple scientific disciplines.

The Risk Assessment Knowledge Integration Platform (RAKIP¹) Initiative has developed various software tools to drive FSKX adoption by model creators worldwide. Over the past years, model creators started to convert their work into the FSKX format and publish them in FSKX model repositories. This white paper is now intended for risk assessment researchers and platform architects that are interested in the latest technological developments regarding the interoperability of the RAKIP-Web platform. For example, publishing an FSKX file in Zenodo² through our RAKIP-Web publication tool automatically generates a URL inside the Zenodo entry that links back to RAKIP-Web – directly allowing the online execution of the model with user defined simulation parameters (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: An FSKX model in Zenodo that can be executed in RAKIP-Web

Providing a way to execute FSKX models online via the RAKIP-Web portal was one of the main features offered to model creators and scientists. However, as the number of models in our repositories increased, the limitations of the original infrastructure became apparent. As new FSKX models were included the requirements to the execution environment changes while there was the need to maintain support for old models created years ago, partly leading to conflicting software dependencies between the different models. To guarantee a functional runtime environment for each model, it was necessary to develop a more robust solution including

¹ <https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/rakip-initiative/>

² <https://www.zenodo.org>

features where also 3rd party developers could access execution services via APIs, as the existing user interface (UI) couldn't accommodate all desired use-cases.

To address these challenges, we developed the so-called “FSKX-Cloud-Platform” - a cloud-based solution that enables the execution of any FSKX model in tailor-made container environments. For each FSKX model, a container image is created with the exact software dependencies and runtime environment required. Through a REST API and event-driven architecture based on the EPCIS 2.0 standard, the appropriate container is deployed on demand, and model simulations are executed securely and efficiently.

This white paper details the architecture, implementation, and benefits of the FSKX-Cloud-Platform, demonstrating how it enhances scientific reproducibility, improves user experience, and facilitates broader adoption of the FSKX standard.

Introduction

Understanding the FAIR Scientific Knowledge Exchange Format (FSKX)

Purpose and evolution

- Originally developed as the “Food Safety Knowledge eXchange” format³ by the RAKIP Initiative
- Recently rebranded as the “FAIR Scientific Knowledge eXchange” format (Filter, et al., 2024)
- Primary focus on efficient exchange of scientific models and associated data

Key problem FSKX solves

FSKX addresses several critical challenges in the scientific modeling domain:

- Facilitates sharing mathematical models and data analysis techniques in a standardized format
- Eliminates the need for error-prone manual re-implementation of models from publications
- Enables direct transfer of executable models alongside data used for training, data generated during simulations and original scientific publications related to the model

Technical foundation

The FSKX format is built on solid technical foundations and uses established standards. An FSKX file is a container following the OMEX (Open Modeling Exchange Format) guidelines. It

³ <https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/fskx-food-safety-knowledge-exchange-format/>

contains all the information to understand the model and the data and implementations to execute simulations. An exhaustive metadata schema⁴ ensures (and optionally exceeds) the minimum information required to annotate risk-assessment models (Filter, et al., 2021) . Model simulations are stored in a software agnostic XML format (SEDML⁵). Figure 2 outlines the basic structure of an FSKX file.

Figure 2: Diagram of the internal structure of an FSKX archive.

Key features

Due to the vast amount of models generated by the scientific community, the need for an efficient way to exchange them together with their data is critical (Haberbeck, et al., 2018). Scientific modelling papers often do not contain the full executable model code, resulting in time-consuming or even impossible attempts to re-implement the models published and to reproduce the results presented in these papers.

The standardized FSKX file format enables scientists to efficiently exchange and reuse accumulated models. FSKX models can be comprehensively annotated using a versioned metadata schema, enabling web-tools to make models findable across the web.

FSKX enables reusability as it include a complete implementation of the model including simulations settings. Usually a FSKX model file contains the model script written in languages like R or Python. Since any implementation requires a specific runtime environment, FSKX metadata provides information about software dependencies as well.

⁴ https://github.com/RakipInitiative/Model-Metadata-Schema/blob/main/genericModelMetadataSchema_104.json

⁵ <https://sed-ml.org/>

FSKX is a machine-readable, platform agnostic format. This simplifies the interoperability of any FSKX model with supporting tools and workflows. Model simulations can be directly executed in any tool able to reproduce the required runtime environment.

Metadata Schema for Model Annotation

The FSKX format includes a comprehensive metadata schema for model annotation, ensuring models are properly documented and described. Key aspects of the annotation schema are (see also Figure 3):

- Providing sufficient information for model interpretation and reuse
- Machine-readable structured metadata format
- Clear linkage between model annotation and executable code
- Open, structured, text-based file format
- Support for controlled vocabularies where possible

<https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/food-safety-knowledge-metadata-schema/>

Figure 3: FSKX model metadata is organized hierarchical. The complete schema can be found here: <https://github.com/RakipInitiative/Model-Metadata-Schema>

Existing Tools Supporting FSKX

Several tools and services already support the FSKX format, including:

- D4Science⁶

⁶ <https://www.d4science.org/>

- MicroHibro⁷
- RAKIP-Web⁸
- FSK-Lab⁹
- FSK2R¹⁰

The technical implementation is based on standardized formats such as Combine Archive, OMEX, SBML, and SEDML¹¹, with support for scripting languages like R and Python.

Problem Statement

While the FSKX format provides a solid foundation for scientific model exchange, several challenges persisted with the existing RAKIP-Web implementation:

Model Execution Challenges

Technical dependencies

Scientists that use FSKX (here referred to as “model creators”) are not limited to certain software languages, packages or versions. If the model code is structured according to the harmonization principles of FSKX (see Figure 4), the model creator has complete freedom over their implementation.

Figure 4: Harmonized code in FSKX models: simulation, execution, output and visualization(optional)

This creates challenges for supporting tools that try to provide an execution environment for FSKX models. Some of these challenges are:

- Models require very specific software versions (e.g., R 3.5, specific library versions) to run
- Version mismatches often lead to execution failures
- Results may deviate from the original due to version differences
- Legacy models frequently become incompatible with modern environments

⁷ <https://microhibro.com/en/>

⁸ <https://knime.bfr.berlin/landingpage/RAKIP-Model-Repository>

⁹ <https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/fsk-lab/>

¹⁰ <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/FSK2R/index.html>

¹¹ <https://co.mbine.org/standards/>

Development and Maintenance Challenges

RAKIP-Web platform issues

The RAKIP-Web model repository¹² was developed by BfR (German Federal Institute for Risk-Assessment) to lay the foundation for the usage of FSKX, providing a central place for finding and executing curated models developed by an international consortium. Although RAKIP-Web achieved the primary vision of FSKX, making scientific knowledge findable and accessible, and in some cases even interoperable (Integration with Zenodo), it always struggled to find a robust way to realize the actual model-execution.

Rigid backend infrastructure:

Running a simulation of an FSKX model was realized by using a KNIME¹³-Server-based backend, which orchestrated the execution of KNIME workflows. The software KNIME provides an open-source desktop application offering a low-code solution for creating complex data analysis workflows and applications. BfR developed an extension called “FSK-Lab” for KNIME that provided KNIME with features for FSKX-file handling, i.e. reading, editing, executing and creating valid FSKX model files. Executing a model meant in this implementation, that a KNIME workflow with FSK-Lab nodes was started by the KNIME server, and the result of the KNIME Server execution was finally presented to the user via a web-based UI. While this approach worked, and is in fact still used for many workloads, it failed to provide an efficient solution for the very diverse set of models collected over time in the RAKIP-Web model repository.

The primary reason for that is, that when running an FSKX-model, the underlying script-code is executed within an R or Python interpreter on the KNIME server. As the available KNIME server had limited compute resources and could only provide a single execution environment for for R (3.5.1), Python 2 and Python 3 (3.6). Whenever new models required additional 3rd party libraries, the addition of these libraries to the existing execution environments on the server frequently broke the existing environment due to unresolvable dependency conflicts. Even more critical, models that required more recent packages could not be supported at all. Additionally, model executions started by a KNIME workflow would run directly on the server environment (“bare metal”). Besides potential security risks, we frequently observed that R or Python processes would not stop after job completion, causing memory leaks and loss of compute resource over time. Another aspect was, that while the installed KNIME-Server version could balance workloads for its native KNIME workflows, it didn’t work for external software, in our case R and Python, leading to overload on the server when models were executed simultaneously.

¹² <https://knime.bfr.berlin/landingpage/RAKIP-Model-Repository>

¹³ <https://www.knime.com/>

Solution: Cloud-based FSKX Microservice Architecture

To address the challenges outlined above, we developed the FSKX-Cloud-Platform - a comprehensive solution that leverages modern cloud technologies and containerization.

Architecture Overview

Our solution uses containerization technology to create isolated, model-specific runtime environments. For each FSKX model, we generate a dedicated container image that encapsulates all necessary dependencies, libraries, and runtime environments. This approach ensures that each model has its own tailored execution environment, eliminating compatibility issues and version conflicts. In most cases, container images are automatically generated based on model metadata (see Figure 5). However, when additional libraries or 3rd party software is required to execute a model, the process of finding the optimal image configuration is done manually.

Figure 5: Automatic image creation from FSKX Metadata

Once a container image has been created for a model, it will be pushed to an image repository. This ensures that even legacy models with obsolete dependencies remain executable for a long time, regardless of the host system.

Though our models are heavily curated and went through several technical and scientific quality assurance checks, we value the extra level of security, that the container approach provides.

Another advantage of the FSKX-Cloud-Platform solution is its scalability: compute resources are only required when a simulation is requested, and since each model has been curated, the exact amount of memory, CPU and GPU power is known to the system.

RESTful API Framework

The FSKX-Cloud-Platform exposes its functionality through a comprehensive RESTful API ecosystem, providing programmatic access to all core platform capabilities. The API framework includes:

- **Container Management Service API** - Handles automated container creation, lifecycle management, and deployment orchestration for FSKX models
- **Model Execution Service API** - Enables remote execution of model simulations with custom parameter sets and real-time status monitoring
- **Model Lookup Service API** - Facilitates model metadata lookup, version control, validation, and CRUD operations for model assets
- **File Service API** - Provides access to simulation outputs, data visualization endpoints, and result export capabilities

All APIs are fully documented using OpenAPI 3.0 specifications, ensuring comprehensive developer documentation with interactive testing capabilities. This standardized approach enables seamless integration with third-party tools, workflow automation platforms, and custom client applications, fostering a robust ecosystem around the FSKX platform. An example is outlined in Figure 6, where an application with proper authorization uses the Model Execution Service API to start a model simulation with user defined parameters and retrieves the results for display.

Figure 6: Direct access to the model execution service API via custom application

Beyond direct API interactions, the FSKX-Cloud-Platform offers EPCIS 2.0 event system integration, allowing the platform to participate in enterprise-wide event-driven workflows, as outlined below.

Integration with Open EPCIS 2.0 Event System

In addition to direct API access, the FSKX-Cloud-Platform integrates with Open EPCIS 2.0¹⁴ event systems¹⁵ to enable seamless communication with existing enterprise infrastructure and supply chain management systems. The idea is outlined in Figure 7: An application emits (“captures”) an event related to a specific FSKX model. In this example, the client application would capture a simulation request event, based on some data it has received. The model execution service of the FSKX-Cloud-Platform would receive notification of this event and trigger a model simulation with data contained in the event. On completion, another event would be released which in turn would notify the client application with the proper simulation results, either directly contained in the event document or as a URL to an external service.

Our platform provides **EPCIS connectivity** through:

Event capturing

The platform can emit standardized EPCIS 2.0 events when significant simulation events occur (model execution start/completion, container deployment, validation results, etc.) – see Figure 7 and 8.

- **Event Subscription** - Integration with partner EPCIS solutions (e.g. developed by Benelog¹⁶) allows the platform to receive and respond to relevant upstream events, enabling automated workflow triggers
- **Standards Compliance** - Full adherence to EPCIS 2.0 specification ensures compatibility with existing enterprise systems and supply chain networks

Figure 7: Application using EPCIS 2.0 events to trigger FSKX simulations

This EPCIS integration enables organizations to:

¹⁴ <https://ref.gs1.org/standards/epcis/>

¹⁵ <https://openepcis.io/docs/epcis>

¹⁶ <https://www.benelog.com/>

- **Incorporate FSKX model simulations into existing supply chain workflows** - Trigger simulations based on supply chain events (shipment arrivals, temperature deviations, etc.)
- **Maintain audit trails** - Simulation events become part of the organization's complete traceability record
- **Enable cross-system orchestration** - Coordinate FSKX simulations with ERP, WMS, and other enterprise systems through standardized event messaging
- **Support regulatory compliance** - Leverage existing EPCIS infrastructure for food safety and quality management requirements

Figure 8: Applications interact only via event communication, no knowledge about specific API's necessary

This approach positions FSKX simulations as integrated components within broader enterprise ecosystems rather than isolated modeling tools.

EPCIS events for FSKX model integration

The FSKX-Cloud-Platform serves as a comprehensive repository for FSKX models and provides seamless integration with OpenEPCIS systems through custom event subscriptions. Our platform's EPCIS integration enables automated model execution triggered by supply chain events. Figure 8 outlines the idea that the FSKX-Cloud-Platform could provide value for existing systems without them directly interacting with our specific API's. An application could just communicate with its EPCIS 2.0 system via subscriptions and still make use of our model execution service.

Custom EPCIS event framework

We have designed and implemented several EPCIS events to integrate FSKX modeling capabilities with existing supply chain systems:

- **Model Registration Events** - FSKX models register themselves with the EPCIS system, making them discoverable and available for automated execution

- **Simulation Request Events** - External systems can trigger model simulations by publishing standardized simulation request events. Figure 9 shows an example, where a specific model (“parentID”) is targeted and the simulation parameters are given as a custom context.
- **Simulation Result Events** - Our platform publishes structured results back to the EPCIS system for downstream consumption

ZL2030 Digital Twin project example

The project “Zukunftslabor 2030”¹⁷, funded by the German Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Community¹⁸ saw a consortium of public and private institutions collecting the results of a variety of lab experiments on food products with the aim of creating “digital twins” of those food product. The state of the food product was captured from sensor data (as EPCIS event) taken at different steps across the food-supply-chain. The idea was that a predictive model, trained on the experimental data gathered within the project, could help to predict properties of the food product (e.g. changes in the microbiota) during its lifecycle. A prototype of such a model was developed and hosted on the FSKX-Cloud-Platform.

As part of the project we developed a proof of concept for the applicability of the FSKX-Cloud-Platform in conjunction with EPCIS:

1. **Event Monitoring** - The platform subscribes to relevant EPCIS events (temperature changes, storage transitions, quality measurements)
2. **Automated Execution** - Simulation request events automatically trigger the execution of the appropriate FSKX model with current product data
3. **Result Distribution** - Prediction results (quality assessments, updated best-before-dates) are published as EPCIS events for consumption by supply chain management systems

The proof of concept demonstrated real-time integration of advanced food safety modeling with existing enterprise systems, allowing FSKX models to operate as intelligent components within broader supply chain workflows through standardized EPCIS event communication (see Figure 9).

¹⁷ <https://zukunftslabor2030.de/>

¹⁸ <https://www.bmel.de/>

```

"@context": [
  "https://ref.gs1.org/standards/epcis/2.0.0/epcis-context.jsonld",
  {
    "fskparam": "https://medifit-prima.github.io/fsklab-json/FSKParameter.json",
    "fskx": "https://medifit-prima.github.io/fsklab-json/1.0.4/FSKModel.json"
  }
],
"id": "fskx:simulation:request",
"type": "EPCISDocument",
"schemaVersion": "2.0",
"creationDate": "2023-10-02T13:01:06.449Z",
"epcisBody": {
  "eventList": [
    {
      "fskparam:parameters": [
        {
          "fskparam:metadata": {
            "fskparam:id": "temperatures",
            "fskparam:classification": "INPUT",
            "fskparam:name": "Temp",
            "fskparam:unit": "Â°C",
            "fskparam:dataType": "VECTOROFNUMBERS",
            "fskparam:value": "tempValueString"
          },
          "fskparam:data": "[2.016973875043611,2.139238601254758, ...]",
          "fskparam:modelId": "43bc4c4e-dd7b-4147-94ab-946eacc58dd2",
          "fskparam:parameterType": "VECTOROFNUMBERS",
          "fskparam:generatorLanguage": "Python 3.10"
        },
        { ... }
      ],
      "type": "AssociationEvent",
      "eventTime": "2024-05-10T11:38:44.449Z",
      "eventTimeZoneOffset": "+02:00",
      "parentID": "fskx:model:uuid:43bc4c4e-dd7b-4147-94ab-946eacc58dd2",
      "childEPCs": [
        "https://id.gs1.org/01/04068226632339/21/1865"
      ],
      "readPoint": {
        "id": "fskx:bfr:z12030:api"
      },
      "action": "ADD",
      "bizStep": "inspecting",
      "disposition": "in_progress",
      "bizTransactionList": [
        {
          "type": "testprd",
          "bizTransaction": "https://github.com/MEDIFIT-PRIMA/data_fusion/tree/main/fskx_models"
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}

```

Figure 9: A "simulation request" event that triggers a simulation in the FSKX-Cloud-Platform

Key Features and Benefits

Containerization of service applications

The FSKX-Cloud-Platform uses a microservice architecture. All components are – where possible – containerized. Exceptions are the native solutions, provided by the host system – currently Amazon Web Services (AWS): The Elastic Kubernetes Service (EKS), S3 storage, Elastic Container Registry (ECR) as well as the Secrets-Manager. We develop the infrastructure using Terraform (“infrastructure-as-code“), allowing us to migrate away to a different hosting system whenever needed.

The decision to use a microservice approach was made for several reasons: Firstly, we wanted to keep the complexity of individual services as low as possible. Each service can be fully understood, maintained and improved, without the need to understand the entire codebase of the FSKX-Cloud-Platform. Should the platform need a new service, it can be easily developed and tested in isolation, before being deployed into the main infrastructure. Our Spring Cloud discovery service will automatically register new service, making it available for other applications within or from outside the system.

Secondly, microservices allow for an easy and targeted scaling. Specifically, the execution of models can require additional compute resources at certain times. Our EKS cluster is configured to space additional worker nodes when traffic reaches a certain threshold (horizontal scaling). Alternatively, if an FSKX model requires more compute, i.e. a GPU, our system temporarily spawns a node that provides the required hardware.

Finally, the big advantage of a microservice architecture is the isolation of its components. Our logging and monitoring services can give specific information about the status of each microservice, allowing for quick troubleshooting where and when needed. And should a microservice fail, it won't (necessarily) affect the entire FSKX-Cloud-Platform.

On-demand model execution

Models are executed on-demand through the API – see Figure 10:

- Users or applications request model execution with specific parameters
- The system identifies the appropriate container for the model
- The container is deployed, and the model is executed
- Results are returned to the requester
- Resources are released after execution

Figure 10: Execution of a model being orchestrated by Kubernetes

Technical Overview

Container orchestration with Kubernetes

The FSKX-Cloud-Platform leverages Kubernetes for container orchestration:

- Automated deployment of containers
- Scaling based on demand
- Load balancing across available resources
- Self-healing capabilities
- Resource optimization

FSKX microservice API architecture

Based on the Model-Execution-Service implementation, the FSKX-Cloud-Platform's API architecture consists of several core microservices that work together to provide a comprehensive solution:

The architecture includes these key components:

- **Model Metadata Service:** Manages and provides access to model metadata, including parameter definitions, requirements, and descriptions

- **Container Management Service:** Handles container image creation, registry management, and versioning
- **Execution Service:** Deploys containers and executes models, orchestrating the simulation process
- **Result Management Service:** Stores and provides access to simulation results, including visualizations and data outputs
- **Authentication and Authorization Service:** Manages user access and permissions via Keycloak integration

This architecture supports five main functionalities as implemented in the Model-Execution-Service:

1. **Run a simulation**
 - Select a model by providing a `model_id`
 - Optionally set custom input parameters (or use defaults)
 - Define visualization preferences (e.g., PNG, PDF, SVG)
 - Receive a `simulation_id` for tracking and result retrieval
2. **Retrieve simulation results**
 - Access visualizations in multiple formats
 - Retrieve output parameters (JSON)
 - Access simulation logs
 - Support for various file types: PNG, JSON, CSV, PDF, logs, SVG
3. **Get simulation information**
 - Check simulation status (pending, running, success, error)
 - Retrieve simulation metadata (status, start/end times, logs)
4. **Model management**
 - Register new models
 - List available models
 - Update existing models
 - Delete models
5. **Monitor simulation status**
 - Track simulation status updates
 - Update simulation database records
 - Capture simulation pod logs
 - Update simulation parameters after successful execution

Integration with cloud services

The platform integrates with various cloud services, such as:

- Container registries for storing images – currently AWS ECR
- Object storage for model and result files – currently AWS S3
- Database services for metadata and system state – currently PostgreSQL
- Monitoring and logging services – currently Prometheus and Loki

Automated container image generation and model execution

The FSKX-Cloud-Platform employs a sophisticated process for automatically generating container images and executing models, leveraging Kubernetes for orchestration (see Figure 11):

Container Image Generation Process

1. **Extract environment metadata from FSKX model**
 - Parse the FSKX file to identify runtime requirements
 - Determine programming language (R, Python, etc.)
 - Extract library dependencies and version requirements
 - Identify resource requirements (CPU, RAM, GPU)
2. **Generate container build script**
 - Create a Dockerfile or Singularity definition file
 - Include base image selection based on language requirements
 - Add installation commands for all dependencies
 - Configure environment variables and execution parameters
 - Add the model code and data files
3. **Build container image**
 - Execute build process for the container
 - Validate successful installation of dependencies
 - Test basic functionality of the environment
 - Optimize image size and performance
4. **Store image in container registry**
 - Tag image with model ID and version information
 - Push to container registry (AWS ECR or similar)
 - Implement versioning and access controls
 - Ensure availability for Kubernetes deployment
5. **Create mapping between model and container image**
 - Update database with model-to-container mapping
 - Store resource requirements for orchestration
 - Include metadata for selection and filtering
 - Configure access permissions

Figure 11: Container image creation process

Model execution process

The model execution process is managed by the Model Execution Service, which coordinates the deployment of containers and handling of simulation results (see Figure 12):

1. Simulation Request Processing

- Receive simulation request via API
- Validate input parameters against model requirements
- Generate unique simulation ID
- Record simulation in database with "pending" status

2. Container Deployment

- Select appropriate container image based on model ID
- Create Kubernetes pod specification with resource requirements
- Set environment variables for simulation parameters
- Deploy pod to Kubernetes cluster with appropriate labels
- Update simulation status to "running"

3. Execution Monitoring

- Watch pod status for updates
- Capture and store logs in real-time
- Monitor resource utilization
- Handle timeouts and errors

4. Result Management

- Capture output files from container (visualizations, data)
- Store results in S3 or similar object storage
- Update simulation record with result locations
- Set simulation status to "success" or "error"
- Clean up Kubernetes resources

5. Result Retrieval

- Provide API endpoints for accessing results
- Support multiple output formats
- Enable filtering and processing of results
- Ensure proper access control

Figure 12: Container deployment process for model execution

Outlook: the Future is AI

Originally, we developed the FSKX-Cloud-Platform as a replacement for the RAKIP-Web model repository, a place to host and run many diverse models with individual requirements in isolated environments that can remain operational for many years. We decided to separate our

Web-Interface from the backend by exposing comprehensive APIs for a multitude of FSKX related microservices to make it easier for our partners to include them into their projects. With the rapid advances made in generative AI however, new opportunities are emerging. Modern large language models that are capable of reasoning can make use of external tools, and AI agents can be designed to autonomously work towards a goal, no matter how complex the task. Figure 13 shows a potential use-case: A person with a food-risk related question uses natural language to formulate a problem. An AI agent reasons that the use of tools linked to our FSKX-Cloud-Platform is appropriate and figures out a workflow that can provide a qualified answer, based on the collected knowledge within our model repository. The Model Context Protocol¹⁹(MCP), introduced by Anthropic²⁰, defines a standard for creating and integrating tools into an increasing number of applications. It is conceivable that we create appropriate MCP servers for the FSKX-Cloud-Platform, ready to be used by anyone with access to AI powered tools or chatbots.

Talk to your model

Figure 13: A conceptual use-case: a user has a food related question and an appropriate FSKX agent uses the tools and the collected knowledge of the FSKX-Cloud-Platform to generate a qualified answer.

Potential enhancements

Future enhancements to the FSKX-Cloud-Platform may include:

- **User-friendly FSKX creation tools:** Making the creation of valid FSKX models simple and quick, with optional AI support, eliminating the off-putting overhead of code harmonization and metadata annotation
- **Model Submission and Curation services:** Model creators should be able to submit their FSKX models into our FSKX repositories, and after thorough quality assurance

¹⁹ <https://www.anthropic.com/news/model-context-protocol>

²⁰ <https://www.anthropic.com/>

added to our curated list of executable models – making them available for the scientific community world-wide

- **Integrated model validation tools:** Automated verification of model outputs against reference data or expected ranges
- **Integration of linked data and graph databases:** FSKX model data will be linked to established ontologies, preventing semantic ambiguities that often arise among diverse science communities
- **AI agent-based interaction:** Chatbots can replace traditional user-interfaces, allowing users to use natural language to interact with our platform

Conclusion

The FSKX-Cloud-Platform represents a significant advancement in scientific model execution and interoperability. By leveraging containerization, microservices, and event-driven architecture, it addresses the critical challenges that have limited the adoption and utility of FSKX models.

Key advantages of the solution include:

- Elimination of dependency and version conflicts
- Simplified model creation and execution
- Enhanced security through containerization
- Improved scalability and maintainability
- Seamless integration with existing repositories and workflows

By adopting the FSKX-Cloud-Platform, scientific organizations can enhance reproducibility, facilitate collaboration, and accelerate scientific discovery through the efficient exchange and execution of models.

CRedit Authorship Contribution Statement

Thomas Schüler: Writing - Original Draft, Project administration, Software. **Sven Böckelmann:** Software, Resources. **Matthias Filter:** Review & editing, Funding acquisition.

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Glossary

- **FSKX**: FAIR Scientific Knowledge eXchange format
- **RAKIP**: Risk Assessment Knowledge Integration Platform
- **EPCIS**: Electronic Product Code Information Services, a standard for sharing event information

References

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Appendices

API Specification

The FSKX-Cloud-Platform API is fully documented using the OpenAPI specification.

The complete API documentation is available through a Swagger UI interface deployed with each service.

Model Lookup Service: <https://fskx-api-gateway-service.risk-ai-cloud.com/model-lookup-service-doc>

Model Execution Service: <https://fskx-api-gateway-service.risk-ai-cloud.com/model-execution-service-doc>

Technology Stack

- **Languages:** Python, R, JavaScript, Java
- **Frameworks:** Next 14²¹, Flask²², SQLAlchemy²³, Alembic²⁴, Spring Cloud²⁵
- **Databases:** PostgreSQL
- **Container Technologies:** Docker²⁶
- **Orchestration:** Kubernetes²⁷, AWS EKS²⁸
- **Storage:** AWS S3, AWS ECR
- **Authentication:** Keycloak²⁹
- **Event Management:** EPCIS 2.0

²¹ <https://nextjs.org/blog/next-14>

²² <https://flask.palletsprojects.com/>

²³ <https://www.sqlalchemy.org/>

²⁴ <https://alembic.sqlalchemy.org/>

²⁵ <https://spring.io/projects/spring-cloud>

²⁶ <https://www.docker.com>

²⁷ <https://kubernetes.io>

²⁸ <https://aws.amazon.com/eks/>

²⁹ <https://www.keycloak.org/>